

William Carey Rees (1845 – 1879): The First Australian Doctor

Peter Stride

MBBS, MRCP(UK), FRACP, FRCPEdin, FRCP, D. Med - research (UQ);
Senior Lecturer, University of Queensland School of Medicine, Australia

Suggested Citation

Stride, P. (2024). William Carey Rees (1845 – 1879): The First Australian Doctor. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 157-166.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).16](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).16)

Abstract:

In 1867, William Carey Rees and Patrick Moloney were the first two medical students to graduate from an Australian Medical School. Prior to that date all medical practitioners working in Australia since the First Fleet in 1788 had graduated overseas, predominantly in England and Scotland. The short career of William Carey Rees before his premature death aged thirty three is described.

Keywords: *history of medicine, Australia, medical career.*

Introduction

The Melbourne Medical School opened in 1862 after the Sydney University School of Medicine opened in 1856, but before they admitted students. Melbourne admitted its first medical students in 1862. In 1867, William Carey Rees was one of the first two students to qualify as a doctor and his short but distinguished career is described. The major source of information is the National Library of Australia digitised newspapers, the Trove website. This is not a peer reviewed source but contains the most information.

Figure 1. University of Melbourne

William Carey Rees

Rees was born in Isleham, Cambridgeshire, England in late 1845 or early 1846, the son of the Rev David Rees. In 1851 aged five, he was living in Braintree, Essex. In 1859, age thirteen, he migrated to Australia with his family and entered the Melbourne University Medical School in 1862 (Ancestry, n.d.; The Argus, 1879a).

The Council of the University announced that candidates for the degree of M.B should study for five years and pass five examinations. Doctors of today would expect the lectures in descriptive and surgical anatomy with practical dissections and chemistry lectures with practical chemistry sessions in the laboratory.

Less taught today would be the comparative anatomy and zoology and structural and physiological botany. A surprise might be lectures in Greek, Latin, Geometry, Natural Philosophy, Geology, Palaeontology and Natural Philosophy.

Once past the basic sciences and admitted to the ward as surgical and medical dressers, the teaching of surgery and medicine is more

practical with an expectation of performing minor procedures. Obstetric medicine, and the diseases of women and children, and practical pharmacy are also taught and examined rigorously, with the award of the degree of Bachelor of Medicine at the end of five arduous and successful years.

In his final examination for the M B degree, Rees received the distinction of 'Scholar of the University' (The Age, 1862; The Argus, 1862; The Australasian,1862).

Figure 2. William Carey Rees (1843-1879), from a Drawing Circa 1870

Rees' first appearance in print was inauspicious. A meeting of the Melbourne Hospital decided to dismiss Dr Patrick Moloney, Rees's fellow graduate, colleague and friend, from his position as resident physician as a result of an 'absence' although no harm to any patients occurred. Rees

resigned his position as resident surgeon in protest.

Dr. Barker, a member of staff wrote requesting a review of this decision which he deeply regreted to no avail. He considered Rees and Moloney were amongst the most distinguished young students in the colony, and that the duties of resident medical officer have never been done so well as since the appointment of these young gentlemen.

The following flattering address, signed by all ninety nine surgical patients currently in the Melbourne Hospital, was presented to Dr. Rees. Melbourne Hospital, May 25, 1868. To Dr. W. C. Rees, M.B., resident surgeon.

We, the undersigned, beg respectfully to thank you for the kindness and attention you have always shown to us as patients during your office as resident surgeon. We feel that it would ill become us as recipients of the charity to call in question any action of the committee, but we deeply regret the cause that has led to your resignation, and, being the actual sufferers thereby, we hope that circumstances may yet justify you in changing your decision."

In spite of these accolades Rees relocated to the Adelaide Hospital (The Age, 1868; The Argus, 1868; The Herald,1868a).

A number of his personal friends and a few of his fellow students at the University arranged a gathering at the residence of his father, Rev. D. Rees, South Yarra, for the purpose of conveying to him some distinct and substantial proof of their estimation, of his character and literary attainments, presenting Rees a gold watch and chain.

Dr. Thomas presided and expressed the immense pleasure he felt in being present on such an occasion; observing that he had known William Rees from the commencement of his medical studies and had watched with the greatest interest his zeal and devotedness in the discharge of the duties of his profession (The Herald, 1868b).

The following year Rees planned to visit England accompanied by his father the Rev. D. Rees, for the purpose of inspecting the best of

the medical institutions of the old country (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1869).

In 1869 he visited England and passed the examination of the London Royal College of Surgeons becoming a member of that college. In 1970 while still in England he became married (The Argus, 1869).

Rees was appointed ship's surgeon to the 'Varuna' for the voyage back to Australia however, owing to a sudden attack of illness on the part of his new wife they were not able to leave England. Rees's father sailed alone and published a letter to this effect. He and the other passengers were most anxious about the lack of a doctor on board (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1869).

On his return from England, Rees was elected as resident medical officer the Alfred Hospital by a large majority of votes from twenty one applicants (The Argus, 1870).

Rees treated a lad named Pirani of Emerald Hill in the Alfred Hospital for probable chloroform toxicity. He was found lying insensible on the waste lands adjoining the hospital and was taken into the institution, where it was discovered that there was a strong smell of chloroform in his breath. Rees applied appropriate remedies, including the stomach-pump, and by the night Pirani was recovering (The Argus, 1871d).

Dr. Rees exhibited a postmortem specimen of ovarian tumour from a patient in the Alfred Hospital at the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria. He undertook to present the tumour microscopy at the next meeting. Rees's paper on a case of chloroform poisoning, presumably Pirani from the previous month, was postponed to the following month (The Argus, 1871c; The Argus, 1871b).

Rees attended a child in the Alfred Hospital about two years old belonging to Senior Constable Hennessy of St. Kilda following an accident. The child was kicked in the face by a horse sustaining two severe facial wounds near the eye and nose (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1871a).

Dr. Rees refused to give a death certificate for a male infant named John Douglas as the death was suspicious. An inquest on the body was held before Dr. Candler and gave a verdict in accordance with the medical evidence that the child died from diarrhoea caused by want of natural food (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1871b).

Dr Rees attended a meeting of the doctors of Melbourne in sympathy for Dr van Hemert. Hemert had been successfully prosecuted and fined for alleged unskilful treatment of an injury to the plaintiff's thigh-bone. It was felt that a great injury both in character and pocket had been done to Dr. van Hemert. It appears that he failed to detect a sub-capital fracture of the femur.

The author is a physician with thirty years' experience of treating medical problems in orthopaedic wards. It is well known that early small fractures are notoriously difficult to detect, even with the aid of X-Rays which were not available in 1870. The surgeon today also has the option of CT, MRI and isotope scans.

As Rees pointed out, the fracture may have occurred when the patient fell in the street or subsequently when she turned over in bed. The meeting considered the four man jury was inadequate and the judge's summation erred. It was agreed by the meeting to appeal to a higher court and to support the plaintiff financially (The Argus, 1871a).

Six years later following the death of Dr. Van Hemert and then his wife a few days later, leaving nine orphaned children, Rees donated two guineas to the appeal fund for the destitute children (The Argus, 1876b; The Argus, 1876d).

Dr W. Carey Rees was gazetted as public vaccinator for the district of Toorak (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1872a).

Rees added to his academic qualification by passing the Melbourne University examination for an MD. The paper noted he was one of the first group of medical students there, he had a scholarship and passed with first class honours and that he was first gentleman who had taken

the M.D. in Melbourne as the result of being entirely trained in the Melbourne University (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1872b).

Dr W. Rees resigned his position as public vaccinator for the district of Toorak, to be replaced by Dr John K. Ramsey, M.D (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1872c).

Rees presented the results of his post mortem examination of the remains of John Spuck at a coroner's inquest at the Hunt Club Hotel, Wurruk before the district coroner Dr Arbuckle. After Spuck had been missing for two weeks, the body was found by Constable Lloyd floating in the Thomson River with a light rope tied round his neck to the end of which a brick was attached. The coat he had been observed to be wearing the night he was last seen was missing as was his purse.

Rees stated the body had the appearance of having been in the water nine or ten days. and was very much decomposed and discoloured. The scalp had been torn off, and both hands very much torn, evidently by some water animals. There were wounds on the body which, he thought, were inflicted before death by some sharp instrument. He was of opinion that the deceased mutilated himself and committed suicide by drowning whilst in a state of temporary insanity.

There was a ragged wound in the left side of the chest, but to such an advanced stage of decomposition that it was impossible to say whether the injury was inflicted before or after death.

The jury returned a verdict to the effect that deceased, a native of Germany, aged forty eight years, was found drowned on the 10th day of December, 1872, but how or in what manner he came by his death there was no evidence to show (Gippsland Times, 1872).

Dr Rees displayed another talent when he appeared at Madame V. Pett's annual concert at the Prahran Town Hall as one of the gentlemen, presumably singers, with a well-known pianist, a prima donna of the English Opera Company

and other ladies (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874a).

Dr Rees advertised in the paper that he had commenced practice in the Toorak Rd. He had been previously working in Sale in Gippsland two hundred kms east of Melbourne.

On his departure he was presented with a handsomely illuminated address, signed by the mayor of the town and a number of the leading residents, The address expressed the high opinion entertained by the subscribers of Dr. Rees's professional attainments, and the esteem in which he was held as a citizen and a gentleman.

It read as follows:

"To W. Carey Rees, Esq., MD. M.R.C.S.

Dear Sir,

As we are about to lose your valuable services as a medical practitioner in Gippsland, we would like this opportunity of expressing the very high opinion we entertain for your professional skill and attainments, and of the esteem in which we hold you as a citizen and gentleman. You settled at Sale only at the request of a number of influential residents, and we regret that so many doctors have since commenced practice as to be entirely in excess of the requirements of so limited a population. We heartily wish you. success on your return to your old field of labour at South Yarra and beg you to accept the most cordial expression of our regard and good-will."

Here follow the signatures of twelve of the most influential residents of the district, including the Mayor and all the principal landowners, bankers, lawyers, &c. Dr. Roe who was Health Officer of the Borough of Sale, received a letter from the Town Clerk to the effect that the Council expressed entire satisfaction with the manner in which he filled the office of health officer, and its best wishes for his future prosperity " (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874b; The Argus, 1874; The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874c).

Dr, Rees was included in a list of eminent citizens, the Victorian 'aristocracy', scheduled to

be presented to a member of the Royal Family at the Town Hall on her visit to Melbourne (The Herald, 1874).

Dr. Rees published an article in The Medical Journal of Australia about the applications of electricity in medicine. He related the history of medical uses of electricity as described by various European doctors, mostly dedicated to advancing medical science, but also a few fraudulent practitioners. Electricity had been found successful in distinguishing trance from death.

He also presented the subject to the Medical Society of Victoria. Rees described the various electrical generators and their applications and his own personal experiences including manufacturing his own batteries.

Rees stated that electricity had been used in the removal of tumours by electrolysis, for amenorrhoea, paralysis of the bladder, constipation from loss of tone in the muscular coats of the intestines, curing aneurysms and rheumatic gout. He personally found it most useful in pain relief and assisting recovery of peripheral neuropathies and relating his first-hand experiences, with in his opinion, most startling and satisfactory results (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874d; Medical Journal of Australia, 1874).

In 2024 electricity is still used in medicine for pain relief with the TENS machine, and in neurology as deep brain stimulation for Parkinson's and other diseases. Electroconvulsive therapy is almost never used today.

Dr Rees was summoned to Mrs Jane Willis, a widowed lady, at home in South Yarra. She had been found by her son lying in a pool of blood with lacerations to her throat and wrists and a razor was by her side. She was admitted to the Alfred Hospital diagnosed as attempted suicide due to a sudden attack of insanity. It is presumed but not reported therefore that she survived (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1874e).

Dr. Rees, of South Yarra, was elected honorary medical officer of the Melbourne Hospital for

Sick Children, in succession to Dr Black (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1875a).

Dr. Rees exhibited a very convenient and effective constant battery, by Weiss, which he had lately received, and explained its peculiarities and advantages. He also exhibited and explained Storer's and Gauffe's induction apparatus to produce an electric current (The Age, 1875).

Dr Rees exhibited and explained several electrical apparatus for therapeutic purposes at the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria. Among these were especially, a convenient and effective constant battery, manufactured by Worth, of London, which he had lately received from England (The Argus, 1875b).

Dr. Rees, of Toorak-road, was an applicant for the office of honorary assistant surgeon to the Melbourne Hospital (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1875b).

Dr W Carey Rees was appointed honorary attending medical officer to the Melbourne Hospital for Sick Children following the resignation by Dr Black (The Argus, 1875a).

Dr Rees raised the issue of titles of honorary medical officers. The Chairman suggested that the honorary medical officers elected to be Hon. Physicians and Surgeons to their hospital should be called as such. The issue debated was whether surgeons should be called Mister or Doctor and whether a Physician with MB but not MD should be called Doctor.

Mr. Gibbs gave notice that at next meeting he would move that a sub-committee be appointed to ascertain the course pursued by other hospitals as to the duties connected with the offices of honorary consulting physicians and surgeons respectively, and to bring up a report thereon, with a draft of such rules for the regulation of officers as the subcommittee may deem proper (The Argus, 1875c).

Dr Rees was recorded at the annual meeting of the members of Medical Society of Victoria as the presenter of a paper entitled strangulated hernia in an infant successfully treated by aspiration. An interesting concept, while surgery

is regarded today as obligatory for a strangulated hernia, theoretically it may be possible to diminish the size of bowel in a hernia by aspirating its contents such that it can now be reduced (The Argus, 1876c).

Dr Rees attended the three year old daughter of Mrs. Merritt, a widow, with severe vomiting presumed due to poisoning. The family saga began when Mrs Burgmann, living next door, threw into Davis's paddock at the back of her house, some small pieces of bread and meat, apparently refuse from dinner. This was picked up and consumed by Mrs Merrit's five year old son and the girl who began vomiting.

A dog, cat and goose all consumed the refuse and died. The animal corpses were removed for forensic toxicological analysis (The Argus, 1876f).

Dr. Rees, was presented with a moribund child with collapse from congestion of both lungs and kidneys following Scarlatina. He injected intravenous ammonia following which the child 'rallied marvellously' for twenty four hours followed by a severe relapse. Repeat intravenous ammonia improved the child before final collapse and death after a further twelve hours.

According to The Argus, this was a case that was absolutely hopeless, and yet life was prolonged for more than thirty six hours (The Argus, 1876e).

Intravenous ammonia was used in Rees's time for impending respiratory or cardiac arrest with only transient benefits. Today, ammonia is seen mainly as a toxic compound. It is used in animals studies assessing alcoholic encephalopathy or rarely to treat systemic alkalosis.

Dr. Rees was appointed public vaccinator for the district of Prahran, in place of Dr. J. K. Ramsey (The Argus, 1876a).

Dr Rees presented the results of his clinical examination and subsequent post mortem examination of James Wilson, a nine month old boy at an inquest held before Dr Youl, the city coroner.

Dr. Rees stated that the deceased was admitted to the Children's Hospital at half-past 2 p.m. on

the 6th inst., on the recommendation of the governor of the Melbourne Gaol.

He was then suffering from extreme debility, emaciation, and a low form of inflammation of the lower portion of both lungs. There were also a number of sores on his body. Rees ordered for him any kind of nourishment he could take, but he gradually sank, and died the next day.

Rees's postmortem examination of the body found that the cause of death had been exhaustion from want of proper food, and typhoid pneumonia.

Elizabeth Bail, head nurse at the Children's Hospital, deposed that Johanna Wilson, mother of the little boy and wife of a bricklayer, brought her child to that institution on the 22nd of August, and that she was told to return next morning, when she would see the Ladies' Committee, by whom she would probably be assisted with work, while the child would be admitted to the hospital.

The mother did not return until Wednesday, the 6th inst., bringing the child, who was then in a deplorable condition through neglect and in a dying state.

Constable Dempster stated that he arrested the mother on the 22nd of May last, when she gave the name of Glasero. He found her drunk in Swanston-street at midnight. She had the deceased infant with her. She was charged with vagrancy and sentenced to three months' imprisonment.

The jury returned a verdict that deceased died from pneumonia and exhaustion caused by the neglect of his mother, Johanna Wilson, who was committed for trial by the coroner on a charge of manslaughter (The Argus, 1876h; Weekly times, 1876).

Dr. W. Rees, proposed the toast of " The Medical School of the University of Victoria," at the annual dinner of the Medical Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1876g).

Dr Rees attended Mrs Elizabeth Jane Morris, aged forty-nine. While engaged in the kitchen, her clothes caught fire, and she was so seriously burned that Dr. Rees, held out no hopes of her

recovery. Following her death, an inquest was held before Mr, Candler and the jury returned a verdict of accidental death (Age, 1876).

Dr. W. Rees, at the request of the committee of the Blind Asylum, kindly undertook the duties of visiting physician commencing eight months previously to replace Dr. Ramsay. The committee and other medical officers tendered their cordial thanks for discharging his duties with unremitting attention (The Argus, 1877d).

Dr Rees was unsuccessful in his application to be elected to the seven member Melbourne Hospital management committee coming last of fourteen applicants in the election (Argus, 1877b).

Dr. W. Rees resigned his position of honorary assistant Surgeon at the annual meeting of the contributors to the Melbourne Hospital. The committee offered their cordial thanks for his assiduous services (The Argu, 1877e).

Dr. Rees presented an exceptionally large urinary calculus just over an inch in all dimensions which he had removed uneventfully from a child just under four years old to the Medical Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1877c).

Dr. W. Rees, arrived aboard the S S George Calder from Adelaide at Hobon's Bay, the Port of Melbourne on July 14th (The Argus, 1877f).

Dr. W. Rees summonsed Mr F. Major for a debt of £1s.11s 6p, alleged to be due for giving a certificate that the defendant was not capable of attending to his duties in the Post Office Department, Melbourne, owing to ill health.

The defence was, the plaintiff as doctor to the Court of Foresters, of which the defendant was a member, was bound to give the necessary certificate. The doctor submitted the bye-laws of the Court did not compel him to give a certificate without payment. A second objection of the defendant that the certificate was given to his son, who was over age, was held decisive and the case was dismissed (The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1877a; The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1877b).

Dr W. Rees exhibited and explained a new combined galvano-faradaic apparatus at the monthly meeting of the Medical Society of Victoria (The Argus, 1877a).

Dr Rees attended Mr. George Laver who died at the age of forty eight in spite of all medical attention. Having been well in the morning, by the afternoon he became severely unwell with what was described as 'English cholera.' Drs Duncan and Langford provided immediate medical assistance and after two days treatment without improvement, a second opinion was requested from Rees, Laver's brother-in-law. Rees injected intravenous morphia and ammonia with relief of pain, but Laver became progressively weaker and died yesterday.

Laver migrated from Braintree, Essex, England and was actively involved in the church and other community organisations. He was a master builder and joiner who enjoyed a most successful business career including working on the Victorian Houses of Parliament. He was twice married and left a widow and ten children (Kyneton Guardian, 1878).

Scarlatina occurred in the Blind Asylum in November when two of the inmates and two of the superintendent's eight sons were attacked by the disease. Fortunately, the treatment prescribed by Dr Rees, the honorary medical officer, and energetically applied by the superintendent and matron was successful not only in preventing the spread of the epidemic, but also in entirely eradicating it.

The committee tendered their cordial thanks to the honorary physician. Dr W C Rees, the honorary surgeon oculist, Mr J T Rudall, and the honorary dentist, Mr G G Barrett, each of whom had promptly rendered his services (The Argus, 1878b).

Dr W. Rees presented himself as a candidate for re-election to one of six positions on the committee of the Melbourne Hospital in the forthcoming poll, and the following week was successfully elected (The Argus, 1878c; The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1878).

Dr Rees attended the weekly meeting of the management committee of the Melbourne Hospital. The secretary reported the statistics of the hospital for the week. Admitted inpatients, eighty four; new cases, out-patients, two hundred and seventy nine, casualties, two hundred and forty five; total for the week, five hundred and eight, deaths, thirteen; discharges, seventy, number of patients in the hospital, five hundred and eight (The Argus, 1878a).

Dr Rees arranged the admission of Henry Mould to the Kew Asylum with the diagnosis of suicidal insanity. The attending asylum doctor subsequently considered he had improved and recommended that he should go out on leave. However Mould was found hanging dead in an outhouse at his residence.

An inquest was held by Mr. Candler at Hawthorn yesterday, regarding this death. Dr George Airey, legally-qualified surgeon was called to see the deceased immediately after he was cut down, deposed that when he arrived life was quite extinct. There was a deep mark in the neck running from one angle of the jaw to the other, and the face presented the appearances of death from strangulation. There were no signs of a struggle.

The jury found that the deceased had committed suicide whilst suffering from insanity, and they were of opinion that no one was to blame (The Argus, 1878d).

Dr Rees attended Hercules Robinson, the eleven year old son of His Excellency the Governor of New South Wales, was lying dangerously ill from scarlet fever at the Church of England Grammar School. The school was closed for a brief period to avoid contagion. A month later he was reported to be recovering well (Bendigo Advertiser, 1878; Kilmore Free Press, 1878).

Dr Rees was one of five hundred and fifty gentlemen invited to a levée held by His Excellency the Governor at Government House to mark the fifty ninth anniversary of the birthday of Her Majesty. The royal salute in honour of Her Majesty was fired at noon by the Sandridge Artillery battery under Captains Swallow and Eves, from the Prince's Bridge. The

day was duly observed as a public and general holiday (The Argus, 1878e).

The death of Dr. William Carey Rees at his residence in South Yarra was announced. Although unexpected and undiagnosed, there is no report of an autopsy or inquest. His obituary detailed his outstanding academic achievements and his character. The Argus wrote,

Dr Rees thoroughly illustrated the completeness of the medical education our own University is able to afford, and his natural intelligence and singular quickness of apprehension had helped him to make the best use of the advantages he had derived from a connexion with our own principal seat of learning.

For a while he was one of the honorary assistant surgeons of the Melbourne Hospital, which appointment he relinquished on being elected one of the honorary surgeons of the Children's Hospital. Here his thoroughly disciplined ability found the best possible opportunity for its exercise, and the admirable care and attention he manifested in the performance of his duties have contributed in no inconsiderable measure to keep up the prestige of this most excellently conducted charity.

As a member of the Medical Society, Dr Rees has contributed several most valuable papers. He had devoted much attention to the subject of medical electricity, and he was steadily acquiring a special reputation in that increasingly important branch of therapeutics.

Dr Rees was married in England in 1870, and he left a widow and two children (The Argus, 1879b).

Probate was obtained to the will of the late Dr. William Carey Rees of South Yarra in the Equity Court. The value of the deceased's property was estimated at £753 (Gippsland Times, 1879).

Summation

Dr. William Carey Rees's medical career was but a short twelve years. He displayed academic excellence, entering Melbourne University with a scholarship and leaving with first class honours

as ‘Student of the University’ for 1867. A tribute to Rees and to the medical school, a clear demonstration that Australia was capable of producing its own very competent doctors. Subsequently he qualified MRCS in UK and gained an MD from Melbourne University.

Rees submitted clinical issues to the Victorian Society of Medicine on five occasions, the first time only four years after graduation. He presented three cases, an ovarian tumour, a chloroform overdose and a large urinary calculus, as well as two lectures on electricity in medicine.

Rees practiced medicine over a wide area, his cases included gynaecology, toxicology, mental health, internal medicine, paediatrics, urinary surgery, burns, trauma and infectious diseases including scarlet fever, pneumonia, typhoid, and cholera. He performed post mortems and examined histological slides. He became a published expert on the subject of electrical practise in medicine.

Rees was elected to senior positions in several hospitals in Victoria not long after graduation. In twelve years he achieved much more than most of today’s medical trainees and junior consultants in the first twelve years after graduation.

References

Ancestry. (n.d.). Retrieved September 10, 2024, from <https://www.ancestry.com>

Bendigo Advertiser. (1878, April 23).

Gippsland Times. (1872, December 12).

Gippsland Times. (1879, May 23).

Kilmore Free Press. (1878, May 9).

Kyneton Guardian. (1878, January 16).

Medical Journal of Australia. (1874, September), 258–271.

The Age. (1862, January 9).

The Age. (1868, May 27).

The Age. (1875, May 6).

The Age. (1876, December 19).

The Argus. (1862, February 3).

The Argus. (1868, June 28).

The Argus. (1869, April 12).

The Argus. (1870, December 23).

The Argus. (1871a, December 9).

The Argus. (1871b, July 6).

The Argus. (1871c, June 8).

The Argus. (1871d, May 12).

The Argus. (1874, March 31).

The Argus. (1875a, July 30).

The Argus. (1875b, May 6).

The Argus. (1875c, September 8).

The Argus. (1876a, August 12).

The Argus. (1876b, August 5).

The Argus. (1876c, January 6).

The Argus. (1876d, June 17).

The Argus. (1876e, June 17).

The Argus. (1876f, March 23).

The Argus. (1876g, October 27).

The Argus. (1876h, September 12).

The Argus. (1877a, December 6).

The Argus. (1877b, February 1).

The Argus. (1877c, February 8).

The Argus. (1877d, January 23).

The Argus. (1877e, January 31).

The Argus. (1877f, July 17).

The Argus. (1878a, February 6).

The Argus. (1878b, January 22).

The Argus. (1878c, January 26).

The Argus. (1878d, March 14).

The Argus. (1878e, May 25).

The Argus. (1879a, April 12).

The Argus. (1879b, April 12).

The Australasian. (1862, February 25).

- The Herald*. (1868a, October 19).
- The Herald*. (1868b, October 19).
- The Herald*. (1874, May 25).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1869, September 17).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1871a, July 1).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1871b, July 4).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1872a, January 27).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1872b, March 23).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1872c, March 23).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1874a, March 21).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1874b, March 28).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1874c, April 11).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1874d, October 10).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1874e, December 12).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1875a, February 6).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1875b, July 17).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1877a, October 6).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1877b, October 13).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1878, February 2).
- The Telegraph, St Kilda and Praban and South Yarra Guardian*. (1869, April 3).
- Weekly Times*. (1876, September 16).